

Catan: Oil Springs

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Keywords

Capitalism, Climate-change Education, Economics, Environmental Ethics, Ethical Decision-making, Natural Disasters, Resource Exploitation, Sustainability, Tragedy of the Commons

Introduction

Catan's expansion, *Oil Springs Scenario*, was created by Erik Assadourian and Ty Hansen in partnership with the Catan team and the Worldwatch Institute in 2011. This expansion introduces oil as a new resource, which adds a layer of complexity to the game. It balances the idea of economic growth with the environmental risks it entails, shifting the focus from growth alone to its ecological impact.

The game's primary goal is to expand players' settlements. Considering the environmental impact and promoting awareness of sustainable development helps to achieve this.

Its target group includes Catan enthusiasts aged 12+, especially those who have not yet learned a lot about climate change and planetary boundaries, making it suitable for casual gamers.

It qualifies as a serious game by integrating gameplay with educational objectives (Caserman, 2020, p. 3), raising awareness of the exploitation of natural resources, incorporating ethical choices, and encouraging eco-conscious decision-making.

The mechanics involve the base Catan rules with added oil resources. Players can use oil for faster growth, but risk natural disasters. At the same time, they can gain points by sequestering oil, emphasizing trade-offs between profit and sustainability.

Facts

Release date:	October 19th, 2011
Developer:	Erik Assadourian & Ty Hansen for Klaus Teuber (Die Siedler von Catan)
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	3–6 players
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	30–60 min
Languages:	English
Environment:	Table in the middle & chairs for each player

Material:	To play this scenario, you need all game components of the CATAN base game.
Price:	\$5 (no longer available; more expensive secondhand)

Resonance & Criticism

Since the Catan game is well known, the Oil Springs expansion was widely played, but it is no longer produced (Catan GmbH, n.d.). Researchers examined "the actual impact of the scenario on people's knowledge, attitude and behavior" (Chappin, 2017, p. 557). They concluded that the game can influence people's awareness of sustainability issues and affect their behavior regarding them. Nevertheless, not all mechanisms work during play: in many rounds, the players who used the most oil won. Maybe the learning effect is therefore more about understanding capitalist mechanisms, moral choices, and their impacts, including the fact that the people exploiting the resources are often also the ones winning.

Game Principle & Process

Catan: Oil Springs builds on the classic Catan structure, while adding oil extraction mechanics and environmental consequences. Players trade, build, and expand as they manage oil, which offers fast growth but increases pollution risks. Players have moderate control over whether to exploit or conserve resources, though random dice rolls and natural disasters limit predictability.

The goal of the game is obvious: to achieve ten victory points by expanding settlements, cities, and roads, and (hopefully) managing oil wisely. The environmental aspect adds depth, as players must balance short-term gains with long-term consequences. Additionally, the game provides immediate feedback through resource acquisition and pollution tokens. Rewards include victory points for "cleaning up" oil, as well as opportunities to learn sustainability principles.

Disasters such as floods and environmental degradation highlight the consequences of unsustainable practices, including the overuse of oil. It also teaches capitalist mechanisms, showing that those who exploit resources and build monopolies are often also the ones winning and being less affected by natural disasters.

Social interaction is integral, as players trade resources, negotiate strategies, and collectively face environmental crises. Tension arises from competition for growth, as well as from frustration when other players use unsustainable production methods. Additionally, it shows how capitalist competition makes it more challenging to maintain sustainable production when other players opt out.

The game draws on ecological and economic theories, particularly the overexploitation of oil and its consequences. It models how individual actions can lead to collective consequences, underscoring the need for cooperation to sustainably manage finite resources.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

The central learning objective of Catan: Oil Springs is to teach players the balance between economic development and environmental sustainability. It highlights the risks of overexploiting finite resources by including natural disasters, which can also cause the game to end without anyone winning. Players learn the need for sustainable decision-making and cooperative strategies to mitigate ecological damage.

The game's mechanics directly support these objectives. Oil offers an enticing opportunity for rapid development, but its use increases pollution, which can trigger natural disasters. Players face choices that reflect real-world trade-offs: prioritize short-term individual gains or adopt strategies that prioritize the long term and are better for the whole world population and nature. These mechanics effectively reinforce the learning objectives by creating tangible outcomes (disasters or rewards) tied to player actions.

The teacher primarily acts as a facilitator, ensuring players understand the rules and guiding discussions during or after gameplay to reflect on the lessons. If needed at all, one teacher is sufficient. Preparation time is minimal if the teacher is already familiar with Catan, requiring only a brief review of the Oil Springs scenario.

Apart from the mechanisms already mentioned, the game's interactive nature fosters critical thinking and discussion, encouraging players to internalize the challenges mentioned above.

Effectiveness

There is limited direct evidence or studies on the effectiveness of Catan: Oil Springs, but one paper (Chappin, 2017) investigates its efficacy. The research found four driving learning mechanisms in the game: competition, managing the commons, learning from disasters, and free-riding the commons. Over repeated play, players adapt to these mechanisms and change their strategies to more sustainable behaviors. The players seem to raise their understanding and awareness of sustainability issues. Although the players' knowledge of sustainability did not grow from playing the game, their attitude and, therefore, their behavior changed. Nevertheless, the sample size of this research was tiny, which is why its results cannot stand alone as evidence (Chappin, 2017, pp. 264–265). No studies on the game experience were found, but since the Catan game's mechanisms did not change much and it is widely known and liked, one can assume the game experience remains fluid and exciting.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game's content is broadly appropriate, but younger players (under 12) may struggle with its abstract concepts or its strategic depth. Additionally, the game suggests that sustainability and economic growth can coexist. This can develop a false image, while it is actually necessary to reduce the demand for ever-increasing growth. Furthermore, the game only addresses the use of oil and not the exploitation of other resources. The fact that monopoly and exploitation

of all natural resources lead to disasters is not made clear. Other problematic aspects were not found.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

Caserman, P., Hoffmann, K., Müller, P., Schaub, M., Straßburg, K., Wiemeyer, J., Bruder, R., & Göbel, S. (2020). Quality criteria for serious games: Serious part, game part, and balance. *JMIR Serious Games*, 8(3), e19037. <https://doi.org/10.2196/19037>

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Chappin, E. J. L., Bijvoet, X., & Oei, A. (2017). Teaching sustainability to a broad audience through an entertainment game – The effect of Catan: Oil Springs. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 156, 556–568. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.04.069>